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Balancing sustainable Mobility and Safety – how to fit e-scooters into urban transport, case Helsinki

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze the current state of shared e-scooter parking and potential parking-related challenges to address in the Kallio district in Helsinki, Finland. In addition, the current status of e-scooter rules and restrictions was collected. Data concerning e-scooter parking was collected with field observations. The results of the study show that further improvements to current shared e-scooter parking practices would improve accessibility and even safety, especially for the vision impaired, those using mobility assistive devices or those walking with baby strollers. Reorganization of parking could be most effective close to the busy transit areas and POI's. Although e-scooters do not seem to replace personal cars, but rather walking, biking and public transport, they seem to be here to stay – at least as one of the solutions for the first and last mile. Hence, finding a balance between the benefits and reducing the drawbacks appears to be relevant.

Keywords: Sustainable mobility, e-scooters, parking

Introduction

E-scooters are an interesting and relatively new addition to the array of various VRU transport options. They provide a quick and easy solution especially for first- and last mile mobility at a relatively low cost for end-users. Moreover, shared e-scooters provide motorized mobility without the need for vehicle ownership. In addition to first and last mile trips, e-scooters can also be convenient for door-to-door trips, and e-scooters can be parked nearly anywhere, representing a viable alternative to driving.

E-scooters could play an important role in increasing the share of sustainable transport options in urban areas. However, they are not entirely unproblematic. The safety related to e-scooters – both riding and parking - has raised many concerns (1, 2), and problematic e-scooter parking practices have posed challenges for other road users by blocking sidewalks, cycle paths and other shared spaces, causing harm especially for the visually impaired and users of mobility assistive devices (3). Shared e-scooters have emerged as a mobility as a service (MaaS) -option in the 21st century and in Finland first in three cities, including Helsinki in 2019, after they became legal modes of transport in road traffic in 2016 (4). Helsinki has since applied various restrictions upon e-scooters and the current city-level restrictions are from 2023 (5). Restrictions concern e.g., the number of e-scooters in the city, speed limits, parking restrictions and limitation of operating hours. All the mentioned restrictions apply already in downtown

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Helsinki but will be further extended and applied to the new areas, which was the motivation for this field study. In addition, a new nation-wide micromobility law restricts the use of vehicles from those aged less than 15 years old and sets a blood alcohol content limit of 0.5 %.

The field study aimed to find out where e-scooter parking currently concentrates in Kallio, where and how parking causes problems to other road users, and hence, where new dedicated parking areas should be implemented.

Methods

Data on incorrectly parked shared e-scooters was gathered in the research area with field observations. An e-scooter was categorized as incorrectly parked if it was not on the side of the sidewalk and parallel to the direction of travel on roadways or cycle paths or parked anywhere outside dedicated parking spaces in pre-defined parking restriction areas close to the subway stations in the area.

An iPad and a survey tool Maptionnaire were used to collect data on-site. The data included GPS coordinates of the exact location of e-scooters that were parked in a manner that causes either inconvenience or even danger to other traffic participants. The incorrectly parked e-scooters were categorized in four categories 1) Sidewalk, 2) Cycle path, 3) Roadway, 4) Outside of designated parking spots in an area where parking is otherwise prohibited.

In addition, the number of e-scooters parked incorrectly in the same location was logged, and photographs (Figure 1) were taken of incorrectly parked e-scooters. The data was gathered in 11 sessions during June 2024 between the hours of 8 AM and 7 PM. The duration of each session was between one and two hours. The start time of the sessions also varied, although roughly equally distributed between morning and afternoon. Only shared e-scooters were included in the data, since the restrictions placed on e-scooters by the city of Helsinki only apply to them. Private e-scooters are only restricted by national law.

Figure 1. Examples of incorrectly parked e-scooters blocking the whole sidewalk and in the car park.

Points of interest (POIs) inside the research area were gathered from OpenStreetMap using overpass-turbo.eu, which is a web based OpenStreetMap data filtering tool. POIs were filtered to bars, restaurants, cafes, food courts, event venues, music venues, nightclubs, theatres, malls, supermarkets, convenience stores, marketplaces, public transportation stops and parks. All POIs were combined into a heatmap with GIS software and further cross-analyzed with the data from the field observations.

In addition, several interviews were conducted to collect the viewpoints of various stakeholders and user groups relevant to this study. The interviewed included representatives from e-scooter operators, traffic safety experts and representatives of organisations representing handicapped and visually impaired persons

Results

E-scooter restrictions and their effectiveness in Helsinki

Helsinki introduced the current restrictions to shared e-scooters in the summer of 2023 (4). The restrictions concern the total number of shared e-scooters in operation within city limits, speed limits, hours of operation and parking. Finnish law also requires safety equipment and insurance for e-scooters over 25 kg (55 lbs) (9). Helsinki has applied different speed restrictions for different times and days. The daytime speed limit is 20 km/h (12.5 mph). However, busy pedestrian areas have a speed limit of 10 km/h (6.2 mph). Weekday nights (00-05) have a speed limit of 15 km/h (9.3 mph). These speed restrictions have already reduced the number of injuries requiring hospital care and the incidence of injuries per distance travelled on e-scooters (1).

Weekend nights (00-05) have a total ban on shared e-scooter operations in Helsinki. Overall, weekends and nights are overrepresented in injury statistics and especially intoxicated users are found to be overrepresented in injury statistics (1, 2). Since e-scooters mainly replace walking and public transport as a means of transport in Helsinki (10), the ban is effective in decreasing injury risk of potential riders and other road users by forcing would-be e-scooter users to utilize alternative and safer means of transport. However, it is unfortunate that due to these restrictions shared e-scooters are beyond limits for everyone, especially since public transport is more limited during the night in coverage and frequency of service.

To reduce the danger and barrier effect caused by the incorrectly parked e-scooters, e-scooter rental companies are required to instruct users on proper end-of-usage parking. E-scooters are allowed to be parked on sidewalks and cycle paths in a manner that does not cause harm or danger to other road users. Users are instructed to park e-scooters parallel to the road and as close to the edge as possible (4). Users are required to take a photo of the parked e-scooter at the end of usage as proof of proper parking. Operators are obliged to monitor photos of parking and penalize users who parked incorrectly. Dedicated parking areas have been established in the city center, nearby areas and all subway and train stations in the city. City parking enforcement is permitted to move harmfully parked e-scooters. One service provider can only have 700 e-scooters inside one restriction area (4).

Finnish law states that it is illegal to operate non-motorized modes of transport while intoxicated, but the law does not state a specific blood alcohol content limit, at least not yet. Cell phone usage while riding is also illegal. However, these laws are very rarely enforced, leading to a common misconception that they are not illegal. Using a helmet is also mandatory, but also unenforced. (4)

Risks of e-scooters to riders and other road users

Accidents involving a shared e-scooter rider requiring medical treatment per one million trips in Finland was 2.9 in 2022, which is a significant improvement from the previous year's 5.0 (18). Finland's value is the third lowest in the EU and noticeably below the average of 9.3. Only Austria and Norway scored better. Studies (15) have found that accident risk varies greatly between e-scooters and bicycles. In a Norwegian study, e-scooters were found to be ten times more prone to accidents than bicycles. Conversely, a British study found the risk to be similar between e-scooters and bicycles. Other Scandinavian studies found the risk to be between 6-12 times higher for e-scooters than bicycles.

Speed limits set to e-scooters are highly effective in improving safety. Even small decreases in speed, for example Helsinki's implementation of a daytime speed limit of 20 km/h from the previous 25 km/h were followed by a considerable reduction in the number of injuries (1). In the same time frame of eight months, the number of injuries requiring hospital care dropped from 528 to 318 after the restrictions were implemented. Lower speed limits allow for greater reaction time, decrease injury risk and the severity of injuries. More than half of all e-scooter accidents in Helsinki happened during weekends before the total ban on weekend night operations was implemented (2).

The average injured e-scooter user in Helsinki is a man in his late twenties or early thirties. (2). The most common injury is head trauma. Out of injured e-scooter users, only 2 to 4% used a helmet. 93% of accidents are single accidents, i.e. they do not involve another party. Before the weekend nighttime ban alcohol played a major role in accidents.

While e-scooter rental companies require that users are adults and only one person can ride on an e-scooter at a time, these requirements are not enforced enough. The death of a 12-year-old in June 2024, who crashed into a car while riding an e-scooter with 3 people on it, proved that enforcement measures are inadequate (16). Currently there are no other measures than the law to hinder multiple users on the same e-scooter.

Results

Incorrectly parked e-scooters were plotted on a map using GIS software. Figure 2 represents all incorrectly parked e-scooters found during data gathering inside the research area. The size of each point represents the amount of incorrectly parked e-scooters found at the location per session. The largest points represent 10 or more e-scooters and the smallest equal one e-scooter. A total of 392 shared e-scooters were found parked incorrectly. Most of them, 293, were parked on sidewalks, 64 outside of dedicated parking spaces in parking restriction areas, 29 on roadways and 6 on cycle paths. On average, 36 incorrectly parked e-scooters were found per session.

To better understand why the shared e-scooters are concentrated in certain areas, POIs close to incorrectly parked e-scooters were analyzed. A key finding is that incorrectly parked e-scooters are most prevalent near subway stations (Figure 2) despite the presence of dedicated parking areas in the vicinity. This demonstrates that the current parking restrictions are poorly complied with. The correlation between other POIs and the location of incorrectly parked e-scooters within the research area is evident (Figure 2). Almost one third of all incorrectly parked e-scooters were parked within a radius of 25 meters from a POI. Since it is likely that not all POIs are recorded in OpenStreetMap, the share is likely even higher.

Parking in the middle of the sidewalk was the most common incorrect way of parking the e-scooter. While mainly an inconvenience for most pedestrians, it represents a significant risk to people with reduced vision, who run the risk of falling due to an unexpected object in their pre-learned walking path.

Furthermore, the change in their walking path caused by having to walk around the scooter, may cause them to be guided to a wrong path, e.g. bicycle path or even on to the roadway. Incorrect parking on cycle paths happened only at a single location, but on three different data gathering sessions. Incorrect parking on roadways was concentrated mostly in the northeastern parts of the studied area

Figure 2. POIs inside the research area (purple heatmap) and location of incorrectly parked e-scooters (coloured points).

There were multiple parking patterns found during data analysis. Potential risk from e-scooters parked on sidewalks varied. Some were not parked entirely parallel or completely on the edge of the sidewalk, whereas others were parked across the sidewalk causing it to be entirely blocked, forcing pedestrians to step on to the roadway and people with mobility aids to take a detour. In addition, e-scooters were often parked in bicycle racks. Users might find them to be logical and less disruptive places to park e-scooters than on sidewalks. E-scooters are, however, potentially preventing bicycles from being locked to the racks by occupying space

Discussion

Shared e-scooters are part of the current urban mobility system in many cities, including Helsinki. They are mainly used for short leisure trips and often as a part of a broader trip chain. Ideally, they would substitute personal cars, but it seems that currently they are mainly substituting walking, biking and

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public transport. Current negative issues related to e-scooters are mainly related to safety and parking. The implementation of dedicated e-scooter parking areas and the requirement to take an end-of-ride photo have not entirely solved issues surrounding e-scooter parking and it is still in the interest of the city of Helsinki to further improve the situation. In addition, even if safety has already improved due to current restrictions, concerns, which include e.g., riding in a reckless manner, multiple riders on the same e-scooter, and riding on sidewalks, still cause danger to e-scooter riders and other road users.

This field study was designed to analyze the current state of e-scooter parking practices in the Kallio district of Helsinki, and hence call for actions to organize their parking. The main results show that incorrectly parked e-scooters were found across the research area and are concentrated close to the transit areas such as subway stations, and areas with a high concentration of POIs. This is aligned with the earlier studies, which show that shared e-scooters are mainly used as a part of a trip chain, and the user is e.g. changing from e-scooter to a subway, bus or tram. A lack of proper infrastructure, mainly sidewalks, leaves users without appropriate places to park the scooter correctly within some parts of the studied area.

Based on the field study, the parking practices in the study area could be improved. Dedicated parking areas should be expanded more broadly across the district and located close to POIs and the busiest transit areas. Unfortunately, the current dedicated parking lots were found to not work as intended. It is possible that the painted spaces are not visible enough, and hence the user leaves the e-scooter in a spot he or she finds convenient. Based on the study, new improved parking areas will be taken into use during the summer 2025 and the impact of these new installations – including both physical parking lots and Bluetooth based geofencing will be evaluated in the fall 2025.

The data gathering sessions were not done at night or during weekends. Night-time is overrepresented in injury statistics, and it is likely shared e-scooter parking is also worse during this time. This would be one additional idea for further studies. Maptionnaire as a tool to gather a location-based data in a field study with a portable device seemed to work very well, even if it has been earlier used mainly as a tool to gather survey data.

Conclusions

The goal of this study was to analyze the current e-scooter situation in the selected Helsinki city district (Kallio) and to assess the need for further restrictions and reorganization for shared e-scooter parking in the analyzed area. Despite the studied area having a relatively high population density and lots of POIs, it does not currently have many dedicated parking slots beyond the subway stations and currently none in the vicinity of the other POIs. The correlation between POIs and incorrectly parked e-scooters was evident. In some areas, the lack of proper infrastructure left e-scooter users without viable places to park in an unobtrusive manner. The results of this study can inform the city of Helsinki, and other cities with similar issues regarding e-scooter parking, to decide how and where to implement new parking slots. Further research will be later conducted on how effective the additional shared e-scooter interventions implemented to the studied area are.

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